

Role of anti-carbonic anhydrase 2 antibodies induced by vaccine antigens, in the etiology of acute myeloid leukemia and other malignancies

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Nov 2019

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Abstract

Cancer can be caused by random mutations induced by radiation, carcinogenic chemicals etc. These cancers are likely to vary from person to person as they are unlikely to develop the same mutations. In hematological malignancies such as acute myeloid leukemia (AML), antibodies directed against carbonic anhydrase 2 (CA2) have been observed. CA2 is involved in maintaining appropriate pH levels in the cellular environment. Anti-CA2 antibodies bind to CA2, hindering its function and thus altering pH levels. Altering the pH can cause predictable mutations. So many people can develop the same mutations as a result.

Epitopes involved in CA2 antibodies have been identified. Bioinformatics analysis of the epitope protein sequence reveals that animal proteins in vaccines are ideally suited to induce such antibodies. Numerous other antigens in vaccines also have significant protein sequence homology to CA2 and can induce cross-reactive antibodies. The immune system normally has strong self tolerance. However, when presented with “altered” antigens (antigens that differ slightly from self, such as animal antigens), along with innate immune system costimulation, peripheral tolerance is abrogated thus resulting in an autoimmune response due to cross reaction. The innate immune system costimulation in this case is provided by live viruses in the vaccine, an adjuvant and/or an allergic reaction at the injection site.

Patients may develop an autoimmune disease first or suffer subclinical autoimmune disease which progresses to cancer.

While this analysis focused on CA2, anti-CA1 antibodies are involved in chronic lymphocytic leukemia. Both anti-CA2 and anti-CA1 antibodies are involved in gastric cancers. It is likely that such antibodies also have a role in acute lymphocytic leukemia (ALL) and other cancers. This can explain why ALL is the most common pediatric cancer and peaks in the 2-5 age range, following the administration of numerous vaccines.

The immune system has evolved mechanisms to protect against cancers caused by natural mechanisms of tumorigenesis. The immune system has no defense against such iatrogenic mechanisms of tumorigenesis.

Vaccines do induce cancers via an autoimmune process. The solution is to immediately remove all non-target antigens from vaccines.

Introduction

Cancer can be caused by random mutations induced by radiation, carcinogenic chemicals etc. These cancers are likely to vary from person to person as they are unlikely to develop the same mutations. In hematological malignancies such as acute myeloid leukemia (AML), antibodies directed against carbonic anhydrase 2 (CA2) have been observed (1). CA2 is involved in maintaining appropriate pH

levels in the cellular environment. Anti-CA2 antibodies bind to CA2, hindering its function and thus altering pH levels (2). Altering the pH can cause predictable mutations. So many people can develop the same mutations as a result.

Epitopes involved in CA2 antibodies have been identified (3). Here we analyze protein sequence alignment between these CA2 peptides and both target and non-target antigens in vaccines. Vaccines contain numerous food (4,5), animal (6), fungal, viral and bacterial antigens (7). Jacob et al. (6) found 293 chicken proteins in the Arepanrix vaccine, for example.

Method

Uniprot (8) and BLASTP (9) were used to perform protein sequence analysis.

Results

Human CA2 was compared with chicken, bovine and porcine CA2 proteins. The 3 epitopes identified by Adamus et al. (3) are highlighted below. In 4 of 9 cases, there is only a single amino acid residue difference. In 3 of 9 cases there are only 2 amino acid residue differences. In 2 of 9 cases, the peptides are identical and unlikely to contribute to autoimmunity. As described before, such “altered” peptides are ideally suited to activate low affinity self reactive (LASR) T cells thus resulting in abrogation of peripheral tolerance (10).

carbonic anhydrase 2 [Gallus gallus]

[NP_990648.1](#) 260 2

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Method	Identities	Positives	Gaps
402 bits(1032)	5e-143	Compositional matrix adjust.	184/260(71%)	213/260(81%)	0/260(0%)
Query 1	MSHHWGYGKHNGPEHWHKDFPIAKGERQSPVDIDTHTAKYDPSLKPLSVSYDQATSLRIL				60
Sbjct 1	MSHHWGY HNGP HWH+ FPIA GERQSP+ I T A+YDP+LKPLS SYD T+ I+				60
Query 61	NNGHAFNVEFDDSDQKAVLKGGPL DGTYRLIQ FHFHWGSLDGGQSEHTVDKCKYAAELHL				120
Sbjct 61	NNGH+FNVEFDDSDK+VL+GG LDG YRL+QFH HWGS +GQGSEHTVD KY AELH+				120
Query 121	VHWNTKYGDFGKAVQQPDGLAVLGIFLKVGSAPGLQKVVDVLDISIKTKGKSADFTNFD				180
Sbjct 121	VHWN KYG F +A++ PDGLAV+GIF+KVG+AKP +QKVVD L+SI+TKGK A FTNFD				180
Query 181	RGLLPESLDYWTYPGSLTTPPLLECVTWIVLKEPI SVSSEQ VLKFRKLNFNNGEGEPEELM				240
Sbjct 181	GLLP DYWTYPGSLTTPPL ECV W VLKEPI +VSSEQ + K R L F+ E EP M				240
Query 241	VDNWRPA QPLKNRQ IKASFK 260				
Sbjct 241	VDNWRP QPLK+R+++ASF+				
Query 241	VDNWRPC QPLKSREVR ASFQ 260				

carbonic anhydrase 2 [Sus scrofa]

XP_001927840.1 260 1

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Method	Identities	Positives	Gaps
460 bits(1183)	2e-165	Compositional matrix adjust.	217/260(83%)	238/260(91%)	0/260(0%)
Query 1		MSHHWGYGKHNHNGPEHWHKDFPIAKGERQSPVDIDTHTAKYDPSLKPLSVSYDQATSLRIL			60
Sbjct 1		MSHHWGY KHNGPEHWHKDFPIAKG+RQSPVDI+T TA +DP+LKPLS+ Y+QATS RI+MSHHWGYDKHNHNGPEHWHKDFPIAKGDRQSPVDINTSTAVHDPALKPLSLCYEQATSQRIV			60
Query 61		NNGHAFNVEFDDSDQKAVLKGGPL DGTYRLIQ FHFHWGSLDGQGEHTVDKCKYAAELHL			120
Sbjct 61		NNGH+FNVEFD SQDK VL+GGPL GTYRLIQ FHFHWGS DGQGEHTVDKCKYAAELHL			120
Query 121		VHWNTKYGDFGKAVQQPDGLAVLGIFLKVGSAPGLQKVVDVLDISIKTKGKSADFTNFDP			180
Sbjct 121		VHWNTKY DFG+A QQPDLAVLG+FLK+G+A+PGLQK+VDVLDISIKTKGKS +FT FDPVHWNTKYKDFGEAAQQPDGLAVLGVFLKIGNAQPLQKIVDVLDISIKTKGKSVEFTGFDP			180
Query 181		RGLLPESLDYWTYPGSLTTPPLLECVTWIVLKEPI SVSSEQ VLKFRKLNFNNGEGEPEELM			240
Sbjct 181		R LLP SLDYWTYPGSLTTPPLLE VTWIVL+EPI SVSS Q ++KFR LNFN EGEPE M			240
Query 241		VDNWRPA QPLKNRQ IKASFQ 260			
Sbjct 241		VDNWRP QPLKNRQ I+ASF+VDNWRPT QPLKNRQ IRASFQ 260			

carbonic anhydrase 2 [Bos taurus]

NP_848667.1 260 1

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Method	Identities	Positives	Gaps
444 bits(1141)	6e-159	Compositional matrix adjust.	208/257(81%)	226/257(87%)	0/257(0%)
Query 1		MSHHWGYGKHNHNGPEHWHKDFPIAKGERQSPVDIDTHTAKYDPSLKPLSVSYDQATSLRIL			60
Sbjct 1		MSHHWGYGKHNHNGPEHWHKDFPIA GERQSPVDIDT DP+LKPL++ Y +ATS R++MSHHWGYGKHNHNGPEHWHKDFPIANGERQSPVDIDTKAVVQDPALKPLALVYGEATSRRMV			60
Query 61		NNGHAFNVEFDDSDQKAVLKGGPL DGTYRLIQ FHFHWGSLDGQGEHTVDKCKYAAELHL			120
Sbjct 61		NNGH+FNVE+DDSDQKAVLK GPL GTYRL+Q FHFHWGS D QGGEHTVD+KKYAAELHL			120
Query 121		VHWNTKYGDFGKAVQQPDGLAVLGIFLKVGSAPGLQKVVDVLDISIKTKGKSADFTNFDP			180
Sbjct 121		VHWNTKYGDFG A QQPDLAV+G+FLKVG A P LQKV+D LDSIKTKGKS DF NFDPVHWNTKYGDFGTAAQQPDGLAVVGVFLKVG DANPALQKVLDAALDSIKTKGKSTDFPNFDP			180
Query 181		RGLLPESLDYWTYPGSLTTPPLLECVTWIVLKEPI SVSSEQ VLKFRKLNFNNGEGEPEELM			240
Sbjct 181		LLP LDYWTYPGSLTTPPLLE VTWIVLKEPI SVSS+Q +LKFR LNFN EGEPE LM			240
Query 241		VDNWRPA QPLKNRQ IKA 257			
Sbjct 241		+ NWRPA QPLKNRQ ++LANWRPA QPLKNRQ VRG 257			

Discussion

Bioinformatics analysis of the epitope protein sequence reveals that animal proteins in vaccines are ideally suited to induce anti-CA2 antibodies. Numerous other antigens in the vaccine also have significant protein sequence homology to induce cross-reactive antibodies. Please see appendix for detailed results. The immune system normally has strong self tolerance. However, when presented with “altered” antigens (antigens that differ slightly from self, such as animal antigens), along with innate immune system costimulation, peripheral tolerance is abrogated thus resulting in an autoimmune response due to cross reaction. The innate immune system costimulation in this case is provided by live viruses in the vaccine, an adjuvant and/or an allergic reaction at the injection site.

Patients may develop an autoimmune disease first (11) or suffer subclinical autoimmune disease which progresses to cancer (3).

Conclusion

While this analysis focused on CA2, anti-CA1 antibodies are involved in chronic lymphocytic leukemia (12). Both CA2 and CA1 antibodies are involved in gastric cancers (13). It is likely that such vaccine induced antibodies also have a role in acute lymphocytic leukemia (ALL) and other cancers (14). This can explain why ALL is the most common pediatric cancer and peaks in the 2-5 age range, following the administration of numerous vaccines.

As always, epidemiological evidence is unreliable (15). Mechanistic evidence demonstrates vaccines do induce cancer via an autoimmune process.

The immune system has evolved mechanisms to protect against cancers caused by natural mechanisms of tumorigenesis. The immune system has no defense against such iatrogenic mechanisms of tumorigenesis.

The solution is to immediately remove all non-target antigens from vaccines.

References

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Appendix

Below are protein sequence alignments between 3 human peptides identified by Adamus et al. (3) vs. target and non-target antigens (soy, peanut, wheat, maize, sesame) in the vaccines. Any score greater than 19.3 increases probability of autoimmunity and thus cancer in this case (16).

Protein sequence analysis included vaccine and wild type viruses to check if there was a difference in protein sequence. No differences were noted.

DGTYRLIQ

peptide-N4-(N-acetyl-beta-glucosaminyl)asparagine amidase A [Glycine max]

[XP_006595853.1](#) 592 1

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
26.1 bits(54)	3.1	7/7(100%)	7/7(100%)	0/7(0%)
Query 1		DGTYRLI 7		
		DGTYRLI		
Sbjct 507		DGTYRLI 513		

nucleocapsid protein [Mumps rubulavirus]

[AGC97176.1](#) 570 2

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
22.7 bits(46)	43	6/6(100%)	6/6(100%)	0/6(0%)
Query 2		GTYRLI 7		
		GTYRLI		
Sbjct 110		GTYRLI 115		

nucleocapsid protein [Mumps virus strain Jeryl Lynn]

[CBA10117.1](#) 549 2

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
22.7 bits(46)	41	6/6(100%)	6/6(100%)	0/6(0%)
Query 2		GTYRLI 7		
		GTYRLI		
Sbjct 110		GTYRLI 115		

glucose-1-phosphate adenyltransferase [Corynebacterium diphtheriae]

[CKG84286.1](#) 477 1

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
22.7 bits(46)	43	6/6(100%)	6/6(100%)	0/6(0%)
Query 2		GTYRLI 7		
		GTYRLI		
Sbjct 108		GTYRLI 113		

Pus6p [Saccharomyces cerevisiae YJM1307]

[AJS19982.1 404 1](#)

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
22.7 bits(46)	41	6/6(100%)	6/6(100%)	0/6(0%)
Query	2	GTYRLI	7	
		GTYRLI		
Sbjct	61	GTYRLI	66	

DUF1834 family protein [Neisseria meningitidis]

[WP_118882916.1 223 1](#)

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
22.3 bits(45)	47	6/7(86%)	6/7(85%)	0/7(0%)
Query	2	GTYRLIQ	8	
		GTYRL Q		
Sbjct	98	GTYRLMQ	104	

Nicalin [Zea mays]

[PWZ16214.1 622 1](#)

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
21.8 bits(44)	49	6/7(86%)	6/7(85%)	0/7(0%)
Query	2	GTYRLIQ	8	
		G YRLIQ		
Sbjct	108	GVYRLIQ	114	

phyloplanin-like [Sesamum indicum]

[XP_011089206.2 154 1](#)

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
21.4 bits(43)	50	7/9(78%)	7/9(77%)	2/9(22%)
Query	1	DGTYR--LI	7	
		DGTYR LI		
Sbjct	82	DGTYRVVLI	90	

hypothetical protein Ahy_A03g010622 [Arachis hypogaea]

[RYR64531.1 1182 1](#)

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
21.0 bits(42)	70	5/6(83%)	6/6(100%)	0/6(0%)
Query	3	TYRLIQ	8	
		TYR+IQ		
Sbjct	245	TYRMIQ	250	

fructose-1,6-bisphosphatase [Clostridium tetani]

[WP_011098885.1](#) 662 1

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
20.6 bits(41)	56	5/5(100%)	5/5(100%)	0/5(0%)
Query	4	YRLIQ	8	
		YRLIQ		
Sbjct	124	YRLIQ	128	

unnamed protein product [Triticum aestivum]

[CDM83847.1](#) 558 2

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
20.6 bits(41)	56	6/8(75%)	6/8(75%)	0/8(0%)
Query	1	DGTYRLIQ	8	
		DGTYR Q		
Sbjct	461	DGTYRQMQ	468	

DMT family transporter [Bordetella pertussis]

[WP_055324292.1](#) 290 1

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
20.6 bits(41)	47	5/5(100%)	5/5(100%)	0/5(0%)
Query	4	YRLIQ	8	
		YRLIQ		
Sbjct	231	YRLIQ	235	

hypothetical protein NTHI1209_00006 [Haemophilus influenzae]

[KIS36594.1](#) 51 1

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
20.6 bits(41)	37	5/5(100%)	5/5(100%)	0/5(0%)
Query	4	YRLIQ	8	
		YRLIQ		
Sbjct	26	YRLIQ	30	

L1 protein [Human papillomavirus]

[AYA94007.1](#) 527 1

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
19.3 bits(38)	102	5/6(83%)	5/6(83%)	0/6(0%)
Query	3	TYRLIQ	8	
		TYR IQ		
Sbjct	433	TYRFIQ	438	

RecName: Full=Nucleoprotein; AltName: Full=Nucleocapsid protein; Short=NP; Short=Protein N [Mumps virus strain SBL-1]

[P21277.1](#) 553 2

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
22.7 bits(46)	0.35	6/6(100%)	6/6(100%)	0/6(0%)
Query 2		GTYRLI 7		
		GTYRLI		
Sbjct 110		GTYRLI 115		

nucleocapsid protein [Mumps virus genotype A]

[AOT98814.1](#) 549 2

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
22.7 bits(46)	0.35	6/6(100%)	6/6(100%)	0/6(0%)
Query 2		GTYRLI 7		
		GTYRLI		
Sbjct 110		GTYRLI 115		

nucleocapsid protein [Mumps virus genotype H]

[ARL00360.1](#) 549 2

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
22.7 bits(46)	0.35	6/6(100%)	6/6(100%)	0/6(0%)
Query 2		GTYRLI 7		
		GTYRLI		
Sbjct 110		GTYRLI 115		

nucleocapsid protein [Mumps virus genotype G]

[AQT03670.1](#) 549 2

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
22.7 bits(46)	0.35	6/6(100%)	6/6(100%)	0/6(0%)
Query 2		GTYRLI 7		
		GTYRLI		
Sbjct 110		GTYRLI 115		

ISVSSEQV

peptidylprolyl isomerase [Neisseria meningitidis]

[WP_124209781.1](#) 520 1

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
24.8 bits(51)	8.2	7/8(88%)	8/8(100%)	0/8(0%)
Query 1		ISVSSEQV	8	
		ISVSSEQ+		
Sbjct 90		ISVSSEQI	97	

erine/threonine-protein phosphatase 4 regulatory subunit 2-A isoform X1 [Sesamum indicum]

[XP_011096473.1](#) 332 1

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
23.5 bits(48)	19	7/8(88%)	7/8(87%)	0/8(0%)
Query 1		ISVSSEQV	8	
		ISVS EQV		
Sbjct 196		ISVSGEQV	203	

Cin5p [Saccharomyces cerevisiae YJM1447]

[AJU08616.1](#) 295 1

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
22.7 bits(46)	39	8/9(89%)	8/9(88%)	1/9(11%)
Query 1		ISVS-SEQV	8	
		ISVS SEQV		
Sbjct 209		ISVSLSEQV	217	

uncharacterized protein LOC100795961 [Glycine max]

[XP_006600359.1](#) 871 1

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
21.8 bits(44)	79	6/8(75%)	7/8(87%)	0/8(0%)
Query 1		ISVSSEQV	8	
		+SVS EQV		
Sbjct 317		VSVSNEQV	324	

unnamed protein product [Triticum aestivum]

[SPT18810.1](#) 891 1

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
21.4 bits(43)	112	6/7(86%)	6/7(85%)	0/7(0%)
Query	1	ISVSSEQ	7	
		ISVS EQ		
Sbjct	379	ISVSAEQ	385	

uncharacterized protein LOC103633296 isoform X1 [Zea mays]

[XP_020396396.1](#) 278 1

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
21.4 bits(43)	71	6/7(86%)	6/7(85%)	0/7(0%)
Query	1	ISVSSEQ	7	
		ISVS EQ		
Sbjct	200	ISVSTEQ	206	

uncharacterized protein LOC112796775 isoform X1 [Arachis hypogaea]

[XP_025695177.1](#) 1242 5

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
21.0 bits(42)	100	6/7(86%)	7/7(100%)	0/7(0%)
Query	1	ISVSSEQ	7	
		ISVSSE+		
Sbjct	255	ISVSSEE	261	

folate-binding protein YgfZ [Haemophilus influenzae]

[WP_105880510.1](#) 280 1

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
21.0 bits(42)	45	6/6(100%)	6/6(100%)	0/6(0%)
Query	3	VSSEQV	8	
		VSSEQV		
Sbjct	61	VSSEQV	66	

phage portal protein [Corynebacterium diphtheriae]

[WP_151450123.1](#) 441 1

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
20.6 bits(41)	32	6/7(86%)	6/7(85%)	0/7(0%)
Query	1	ISVSSEQ	7	
		ISVS EQ		
Sbjct	261	ISVSPEQ	267	

L1, partial [Human papillomavirus]

[CAB54541.1](#) 127 1

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
20.2 bits(40)	46	6/8(75%)	6/8(75%)	0/8(0%)
Query 1		ISVSSEQV	8	
		ISV SE V		
Sbjct 18		ISVTSEDV	25	

bifunctional proline oxidoreductase/transcriptional repressor [Bordetella pertussis]

[CPP15721.1](#) 1287 1

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
18.9 bits(37)	76	5/7(71%)	6/7(85%)	0/7(0%)
Query 1		ISVSSEQ	7	
		+ VSSEQ		
Sbjct 213		VAVSSEQ	219	

QPLKNRQ

pentatricopeptide repeat-containing protein At3g09040, mitochondrial [Zea mays]

[XP_008669178.1](#) 1046 2

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
22.7 bits(46)	37	6/6(100%)	6/6(100%)	0/6(0%)
Query 1		QPLKNR	6	
		QPLKNR		
Sbjct 8		QPLKNR	13	

MULTISPECIES: DNA (cytosine-5-)-methyltransferase [Neisseria]

[WP_002256347.1](#) 419 1

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Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
22.7 bits(46)	37	6/6(100%)	6/6(100%)	0/6(0%)
Query 2		PLKNRQ	7	
		PLKNRQ		
Sbjct 224		PLKNRQ	229	

uncharacterized protein LOC112805396 [Arachis hypogaea]

[XP_025703570.1](#) 385 1

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
22.7 bits(46)	37	6/6(100%)	6/6(100%)	0/6(0%)
Query	1	QPLKNR	6	
		QPLKNR		
Sbjct	253	QPLKNR	258	

MULTISPECIES: hypothetical protein [Haemophilus]

[WP_105903807.1](#) 184

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Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
22.7 bits(46)	20	6/6(100%)	6/6(100%)	0/6(0%)
Query	2	PLKNRQ	7	
		PLKNRQ		
Sbjct	17	PLKNRQ	22	

beta-galactosidase isoform X1 [Glycine max]

[XP_014620886.1](#) 839

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Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
21.8 bits(44)	40	7/8(88%)	7/8(87%)	1/8(12%)
Query	1	QP-LKNRQ	7	
		QP LKNRQ		
Sbjct	740	QPTLKNRQ	747	

tobamovirus multiplication protein 2A [Sesamum indicum]

[XP_011070225.1](#) 281 1

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Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
20.6 bits(41)	72	6/7(86%)	6/7(85%)	0/7(0%)
Query	1	QPLKNRQ	7	
		QPL NRQ		
Sbjct	210	QPLINRQ	216	

GntR family transcriptional regulator [Corynebacterium diphtheriae]

[WP_143338855.1](#) 265 1

[GenPeptGraphics](#)[Next Match](#)[Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
20.2 bits(40)	103	7/12(58%)	7/12(58%)	5/12(41%)
Query	1	QPL-----KNRQ	7	
		QPL KNRQ		
Sbjct	243	QPLLSILEKNRQ	254	

Arp2p [Saccharomyces cerevisiae JAY291]

[EEU04954.1](#) 392 1

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Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps
19.7 bits(39)	114	5/6(83%)	6/6(100%)	0/6(0%)
Query	2	PLKNRQ	7	
		PLKNR+		
Sbjct	116	PLKNRE	121	